

Accessible Learning Labs

Badge Application

Due to the public nature of the labs, the authors are applying for the Available badge. We believe that the Accessible Learning Labs artifact deserves the Available badge because of the important need that the artifact fills. Inequitable and inaccessible software is an unfortunately common problem. We believe that by educating software developers and other members of the software community, we will raise awareness regarding bias, accessibility, and equity in software.